

ANALYZING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF NATIONAL ENVIRONMENT POLICY TO REDUCE PESTICIDE POLLUTION IN THE TEA SECTOR

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Abstract

Tea is a popular health beverage in the world, produced from the leaves of the evergreen shrub *Camellia sinensis*. Tea is a major cash crop and an export commodity in Bangladesh. It's estimated that people drink around three billion cups every day. However, tea plantations are threatened by pests, and planters/farmers must find effective ways to stop them. Chemical pesticides are used widely in agriculture. They play a significant role in many types of farming, including tea plantations. However, due to the potential environmental and health risks associated with their use, pesticides are beginning to alarm consumers and producers alike. The study was conducted to analyze the effectiveness of national environment policy to reduce pesticide pollution in the tea sector. For the survey, relevant data were collected from secondary and primary sources such as books, journals, newspapers, and websites. Both quantitative and qualitative information were used to conduct the study. Data were also collected through questionnaires, interviews, Focus Group Discussions (FGD), and online surveys. Most of the respondents were planters (62.20%) followed by government officials (29.70%). The educational level of respondents consists of SSC to PhD. Most respondents belong to the Masters category (66.20%), followed by the Bachelor category (24.30%). The result revealed that most respondents are 41-50 yrs (32.40%), followed by 31-40 yrs (29.70%). Results revealed that most respondents (47.30%) replied that all the measures (Chemical, Biological, Cultural, Plant Extracts, Yellow Sticky Traps, etc.) were taken to control tea pests. 70.30% of respondents agreed that the environment is polluted due to the indiscriminate use of pesticides. 60.80% of respondents have sound knowledge about environmental pollution due to the indiscriminate use of pesticides in the tea garden. 67.60% of respondents knew the National Environment Policy 2018 and 64.90% implemented it in their tea gardens, which is appreciated. Most of the respondents replied that Joddha (Dinotefuran), ShengLi (Emamectin Benzoate + Thiamethoxam), Calypso (Thiacloprid), Admire (Imidacloprid), Magistar (Fenazaquin) and Automida (Acephate + Imidacloprid) used in their tea gardens. However, 90.50% knew the integrated pest management (IPM) techniques. Most respondents (41.90%) used bio-pesticides as the integrated pest management (IPM) technique, which is much appreciated. However, the rest of the respondents used botanicals, yellow sticky traps, solar light traps, termite queen collections, bracon parasitoids, etc. It was found that 100% of respondents did not use dirty dozen chemicals such as DDT, Heptachlor, Dieldrin, etc. in their tea garden, which is much appreciated. 59.50% of respondents agreed that awareness building, training & motivation, the introduction of IPM in the tea gardens, organic farming, punishment, and finally, updating the policy could make environment policy more effective in the tea sector.

Keywords: Agriculture, Environment Policy, Pesticide Pollution, Policy evaluation, Tea Sector, Organic Farming, IPM, Bangladesh

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Introduction

On a global scale, agriculture holds immense importance. Bangladesh relies predominantly on agriculture, which plays a pivotal role in driving its swift economic progress. The agricultural sector is indispensable to the nation's overarching economic development. Crops, animal husbandry, forestry, and fisheries account for 41.74% of the nation's GDP and employ roughly 41% of the working force (BBS, 2017). Pesticides are one of the most important tools for protecting crops from insects and disease infestation. Pesticides have the potential to seep into groundwater and surface water bodies via runoff and infiltration, leading to water pollution and diminishing the availability of clean water. Additionally, pesticides may infiltrate soils and groundwater, thereby compromising the safety of drinking water. Furthermore, airborne pesticides from spraying activities can spread and contaminate the air. These chemicals can also taint soil, turf, water sources, and vegetation. Beyond their intended targets of insects and weeds, pesticides threaten other organisms, including fish, birds, beneficial insects, and non-target plants.

Tea is a popular health beverage in the world, produced from the leaves of the evergreen shrub *Camellia sinensis*. Tea is a major cash crop and an export commodity in Bangladesh. Now, there are 168 tea estates and more than 8,000 small tea gardens having about 66,000 hectares of tea plantation producing about 102.918 million kg of finished tea per annum with an average yield of about 1,700 kg per hectare in Bangladesh, contributing 1% of GDP (BTB, 2023). The tea plant is subjected to the attack of several insects, mites & nematodes. In the world tea, 1034 species of arthropods (insects & mites) and 82 species of nematodes are associated with tea plants (Chen and Chen, 1989). Among them, 25 species of insects, 4 species of mites and 10 species of nematodes are recorded from Bangladesh (Ahmed, 2005; Mamun and Ahmed, 2011). About 10-15% of its crop could be lost by various pests, particularly insects, mites and nematodes (Sana, 1989). To combat these pests, different groups of pesticides like organochlorine, organophosphate, pyrethroids, carbamates and some unclassified groups have been used in the tea fields since 1960. Chemical pesticides have been used for a long time but have serious drawbacks, such as direct toxicity to beneficial insects, fishes and human beings; pesticide-induced resistance, health hazards and increased environmental social costs and undesirable pesticide residue in made tea (Mamun, 2019). To rid tea gardens of weeds, producers use the harmful chemical glyphosate, mainly under the brand name Roundup, as a herbicide; the chemical is banned in 33 countries due to its adverse impacts on biodiversity (Kudsk and Mathiassen, 2020). Despite concern among agriculturists and environmentalists, the government has yet to take any initiative to control the use of harmful chemicals (Parvin, 2024).

A good environment is essential for a good life. Environmental pollution is one of the most critical burning issues in Bangladesh. It includes air, water and soil pollution. Ministry of Environment, Forest and Climate Change, Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh has enacted [National Environment Policy-2018](#). The National Environment Policy envisaged environment conservation, pollution control, biodiversity conservation, and mitigation of the adverse effects of climate change to ensure sustainable development. Agriculture is one of the prime areas/sectors of that environmental policy. Among the various specific measures, using natural bio-fertilizers and biopesticides is encouraged instead of applying agrochemicals and artificial materials, which should be controlled for adverse environmental impact. It's time to reduce pesticide pollution in the agriculture sector.

In the context of land degradation, declining productivity and quantity of agricultural land and, increasing population and ensuring food security in the context of addressing the adverse effects of climate change, the following policies should be followed to ensure sustainable agriculture:

- Organic farming should be given priority. In order to reduce agricultural pollution and soil pollution, the use of all types of chemical substances in agriculture should be controlled and the use of different types of bio-fertilizers and bio-pesticides should be encouraged.
- In order to preserve the biodiversity of the open reservoir, the use of harmful pesticides in the crop fields surrounding/inside the reservoir should be completely avoided. If necessary, environmentally friendly IPM should be introduced.
- The use of persistent organic pollutants and pesticides should be controlled.

The study aims to address and evaluate the National Environment Policy 2018 to reduce pesticide usage in the tea sector. The usage of pesticides on tea plantations in Bangladesh is largely governed by the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh under the Plant Protection Wing, Department of Agricultural Extension, Ministry of Agriculture and Bangladesh Tea Research Institute, an organ of Bangladesh Tea Board. However, different tea gardens or small tea growers use pesticides indiscriminately, ignoring the environmental policy. From the above point of view, very few studies have been conducted on this topic in Bangladesh. In Bangladesh, organic farming has started for various crops but is limited to the tea sector. The study will also focus on the organic farming issue in the tea sector to reduce pesticide pollution. This study will examine the effectiveness of environmental policy in reducing pesticide pollution in the tea sector. Additionally, the study may serve as a reference for future research in this area. Therefore, this study aims to assess the effectiveness of environmental policies in mitigating pesticide pollution within the tea sector.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted to analyze the effectiveness of national environment policy to reduce pesticide pollution in the tea sector. For the survey, relevant data were collected from secondary and primary sources such as books, journals, newspapers, and websites. Both quantitative and qualitative information were used to conduct the study. Data were collected through questionnaires, interviews, Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and online surveys. Seventy-four (74) respondents of different age group & professions participated in the research. A total of 12 questions were supplied to the respondents of different groups. Analyzing the effectiveness of national environment policy to reduce pesticide pollution in the agriculture sector got special attention to the tea sector, which was done by a well-prepared questionnaire.

Results and Discussion

Seventy-four (74) respondents of different age groups & professions participated in the research (Table 1).

Table 1. Percent of respondents participated in the study.

Pameter	Percentage (%) of respondents
Age	
<30	6 (8.10)
30-40	22 (29.70)
41-50	24 (32.40)
51-60	17 (23.00)
>60	5 (6.80)
Gender	
Male	71 (95.90)
Female	3 (4.10)
Prefer not to say	0 (0.00)
Education	
PhD	5 (6.80)
Masters	49 (66.20)
Bachelor	18 (24.30)
HSC	1 (1.40)
SSC	1 (1.40)
None of above	0 (0.00)
Profession	
Government	12 (16.20)
NGO	2 (2.70)
Researcher	10 (13.50)
Planters	46 (62.20)
Farmers	0 (0.00)
Students	2 (2.70)
Others	2 (2.70)

A total of 12 questions were supplied to the respondents of different groups. Most of the respondents were planters (62.20%) followed by government officials (29.70%). The educational level of respondents consists of SSC to PhD. Most respondents belong to the Masters category (66.20%) followed by the Bachelor category (24.30%). People of different age groups participated in the study. The result revealed that most respondents are 41-50 yrs (32.40%) followed by 31-40 yrs (29.70%).

The question-wise analysis is described below:

1) What measures have you taken in the context of tea pest management?

The first question was regarding the context of tea pest management. Most of the respondents (47.30) replied that all the measures had been taken to control tea pests. However, 41.90% of respondents answered that chemical control is the main measure in pest management in their tea garden.

2) Is there any environmental pollution due to the use of pesticide in tea gardens?

The second question was regarding the environmental pollution due to the use of pesticide. Most of the respondents (70.30%) agreed that the environment is polluted due to pesticide use.

3) How the applications of pesticides pollute the environment in tea gardens?

The third question was regarding the effect of pesticides on environmental pollution. Most of the respondents (60.80%) have a good idea of environmental pollution due to the indiscriminate use of pesticides in tea gardens. Secondly, about 25.70% of respondents agree to leaching/washing out the pesticide to the water bodies in their tea gardens.

4) Do you know about the National Environment Policy 2018?

The fourth question was about the National Environment Policy 2018. Most respondents, i.e. 67.60%, knew the National Environment Policy 2018. Unfortunately, the rest of the 32.40% of respondents do not know about the policy. The government/Bangladesh Tea Board has to initiate awareness among the planters through training, seminars, workshops, etc.

5) Do you implement the policy in your tea garden?

The fifth question was about implementing the national environment policy in the tea garden. 64.90% of respondents implement the national environment policy in their tea gardens, which is appreciated. Unfortunately, 35.10% of respondents do not implement the policy in their tea garden. The government/Bangladesh Tea Board has to take the necessary initiative to implement the policy in the tea gardens and small holding tea by imposing, motivation, training, seminar, workshop etc.

6) What type of pesticides do you use in your tea garden?

The sixth question was about the types of pesticides used in the tea garden. Most of the respondents replied Joddha (Dinotefuran), ShengLi (Emamectin Benzoate + Thiamethoxam), Calypso (Thiacloprid), Admire (Imidacloprid), Magistar (Fenzaquin) and Automida (Acephate + Imidacloprid) in their tea gardens. Joddha is the first choice of tea planters. Joddha (Dinotefuran) is an insecticide of the neonicotinoid class for control of insect pests such as aphids, whiteflies, thrips, leafhoppers, leafminers, sawflies, mole cricket, white grubs, lacebugs, billbugs, beetles, mealybugs, and cockroaches on leafy vegetables. However, In July 2013, the state of Oregon of US temporarily restricted the use of dinotefuran pending the results of an investigation into a large bee kill.

7) Do you know the Integrated Pest Management (IPM) techniques for safe tea production?

The seventh question was about integrated pest management (IPM) techniques. Most of the respondents (90.50%) knew the integrated pest management (IPM) strategies that is very much appreciated. However, only 9.50% of respondents do not know the integrated pest management (IPM) techniques. The government, Bangladesh Tea Board, and Bangladesh Tea Research Institute must take the necessary initiative to promote IPM in the tea gardens through motivation, training, seminars, workshops, etc.

8) What measures you have taken for the control of pests & diseases rather than pesticides?

The eighth question was alternative measures taken for the control of pests & diseases rather than pesticides. Most of the respondents (41.90%) used bio-pesticides as the integrated pest management (IPM) technique, which is much appreciated. However, the rest of the respondents used Botanicals, yellow sticky traps, solar light traps, termite queen collections, bracon parasitoids etc. No respondents used entomopathogens. Entomopathogens, bacterial, viral or fungal, are pathogens that kill or seriously disable insects. They play a vital role in the natural regulation of insect pests. The government, Bangladesh Tea Board, and Bangladesh Tea Research Institute have to take the necessary initiative to promote IPM in the tea gardens and small tea holdings through motivation, training, seminars, workshops, etc.

9) Have you used dirty dozen chemicals such as DDT, Heptachlor, Dieldrin etc. in your tea garden?

The ninth question was the use of dirty dozen chemicals such as DDT, Heptachlor, Dieldrin etc., in the tea garden. The survey found that 100% of respondents did not use dirty dozen chemicals such as DDT, Heptachlor, Dieldrin etc. in their tea garden, which is appreciated.

10) What can be done to make the environment policy more effective in the tea sector?

The tenth question was about making the environment policy more effective in the tea sector. The survey found that most respondents (59.50%) agreed to awareness building, training & motivation, the introduction of IPM in the tea gardens, organic farming, punishment and finally, updating the policy. They realize the importance of implementing an environmental policy in the tea garden.

11) As no standard set of benchmark of pesticide presence in the soil or water & no punishment imposed in environment law/rules. Are these the limitations of the policy?

The eleventh question was the limitations of the policy. From the survey, it is found that most of the respondents (67.60%) agreed that there is no standard set of benchmark of pesticide presence in the soil or water & no punishment imposed in environment law/rules. These are the important limitations of the policy.

12) Do you believe that Organic farming or IPM technique is the important tools to reduce the pesticide pollution in tea gardens?

The final question was regarding organic farming or IPM techniques to reduce the pesticide pollution in tea gardens. The survey found that most respondents, i.e. 86.50%, agreed that organic farming or the IPM technique is an important tool for reducing pesticide pollution in tea gardens.

Conclusion

Tea is an export-oriented commodity, hence in order to get around non-tariff trade barriers under World Trade Organisation (WTO) regimes, all necessary steps must be taken to maintain residues well below the Maximum Residue Limit (MRL). In general, Pre Harvest Index (PHI) of tea is to be considered 7-10 days as per Good Agricultural Practice (GAP). When necessary, only BTRI-recommended insecticides with permitted doses should be used. The safe harvest interval following pesticide application is seven days. For the safety of tea production and the preservation of biodiversity, every tea garden must abide by environmental policy. The most important component of chemical control measures under IPM strategy is the administration of pesticides in a need-based, prudent, and safe manner. Learning IPM techniques is necessary to save the environment by keeping an eye on crop health and preserving the possibility of natural bio-control before using chemical pesticides as a last resort. Pesticides will continue to be a crucial part of any plan for managing pests. The choice, application method, dosage, and timing of pesticides are vital factors in the efficient management of insect pests in tea.

Recommendations

The following suggestions and recommendations should be followed for sustainable pest management of tea in the context of environment policy:

- Organic farming or IPM techniques should be introduced in tea gardens.
- Awareness building among the planters should be created.

- Training & motivation should be done to implement environment policy in the tea garden.
- The policy may be updated by incorporating a standard set of benchmarks of pesticide presence in the soil or water & punishment imposed in environment law/rules.
- Monitoring the incidence of pests by assessing their populations in the field should be done.
- Economic Threshold Level (ETL) values of the pests should be followed.
- Appropriate control measures should be started at the beginning of the season.
- Use plant-origin biopesticides for biorational pest control
- Pesticides should be applied only when it is absolutely essential.
- Use only the pesticides which are recommended by Bangladesh Tea Research Institutes.
- Follow the recommended dosage and dilution rates stipulated for each pesticide. Spraying should be done with the approved pesticide only after plucking.
- Samples of tea may be analyzed for the residues of commonly used pesticides.

Collaboration between all the tea estates and the Rainforest Alliance should be needed for reducing pesticides in tea. In our country, tea estates belong to Duncan Brothers (Bangladesh) Ltd. and Kazi & Kazi Tea Estates strictly follow the rules and regulations of Rainforest Alliance. They are also certified by the Rainforest Alliance. The Alliance launched an integrated pest management (IPM) task force for the tea sector. Finally, it is concluded that awareness building, training & motivation, the introduction of IPM in the tea gardens, organic farming, punishment, and finally, updating the policy could make environment policy more effective in the tea sector.

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